

EMBEDDING OF FIBER OPTIC SENSORS UNDER INDUSTRIAL CONDITIONS AND DISTRIBUTED STRAIN SENSING IN TYPE 4 COMPOSITE PRESSURE VESSELS

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ABSTRACT

The number of in-operation composite pressure vessels is increasing, partly due to their attractiveness for on-board compressed gas storage and transport applications. A possible way to maintain the highest safety levels is through the structural health monitoring of the composite cylinders. Here, the use of fiber optic sensors appears to be a promising approach. However, the integration of the optical fibers into the composite structure of a pressure vessel has been shown to be challenging. In this study, insights on the embedding of optical fibers in the composite structure under industrial conditions are provided. A protection concept for the ingress and egress of the optical fibers is presented. Finally, the results from destructive slow burst tests are evaluated, showing no clear trend in the impact of the embedded optical fibers on the performance of composite pressure vessels.

1 INTRODUCTION

Composite materials play a major role in the transition toward a green economy. In the context of hydrogen technologies, composites are widely used for manufacturing composite pressure vessels,

which are used to transport and store hydrogen gas. Among the different types of pressure vessels, type 4 cylinders, consisting of a fully composite wrapped polymer liner, show the highest weight-saving potential. They are also characterized by the capability to withstand the highest working pressures [1, 2]. This makes them particularly attractive for on-board and transportation applications. However, the structural mechanical behavior of type 4 composite pressure vessels (CPVs) still needs to be better understood to precisely estimate their burst pressures and end-of-life performance.

A promising approach is the application of structural health monitoring (SHM) systems, both for the research purposes and for future applications in mass produced composite cylinders. Among other methods, such as acoustic emission or guided waves, in-situ strain monitoring with fiber optic sensors (FOS) delivers important information on the condition of the composite structure [3, 4]. FOS have been widely used for structural health monitoring of composite structures, with CPVs being one of the main applications [5-12]. However, the details of embedding optical fibers are either not described in the publications or do not correspond to industrial conditions. In practical applications, the integration of optical fibers in the composite structure proves to be challenging and time-consuming. To increase the competitiveness of FOS for the industrial applications, efficient processes for embedding optical fibers in composite cylinders need to be established. Furthermore, the FOS can be considered as a foreign body in the composite material, which can have an impact on its structural mechanical behavior.

In this study a setup for the integration of FOS in 6.8-liter type 4 CPVs was developed. The embedding of the optical fibers in the composite structure was integrated into an industrial filament winding process. The manufactured cylinders were tested in destructive slow burst tests. A comparison of the measured strains with finite element models is provided. Finally, the impact of the embedded optical fibers on the performance of the cylinders in slow burst tests (SBT) is discussed.

2 MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1 Composite Pressure Vessels and Fiber Optic Sensors

Optical fibers were integrated into multiple composite layers of six 6.8-liter type 4 CPVs. The cylinders used, consisting of a PET liner as well as helical and hoop carbon fiber reinforced plastic (CFRP) layers, were designed for a nominal working pressure of 300 bar and test pressure PH of 450 bar. Figure 1 schematically shows the stacking sequence of the CPVs used. The helical and hoop layers with embedded FOS are marked. In total, the optical fibers were integrated into 6 of 15 CFRP layers. However, only 3 FOS were used to do so, each of which was embedded in two layers.

Three samples of wet filament wound CPV were used in the study to ensure the reproducibility of the outcomes. These samples differed in manufacturing parameters and loading history before the destructive slow burst test. However, the materials used, geometry, stacking sequence and processing time were the same. Each sample consisted of two cylinders with embedded FOS and three without optical fibers. The three samples are called Sample A, Sample B and Sample C for the sake of clarity:

1. Sample A: wound with a constant internal pressure in the liner, conditioned for 1000 hours under 450 bar and 65°C before slow burst tests;
2. Sample B: wound with an increasing internal pressure in the liner (see [13]), subjected to slow burst tests in a pristine state;
3. Sample C: wound with an increasing internal pressure in the liner, conditioned for 1000 hours under 450 bar and 65°C before slow burst tests.

Optical fibers SM1500(6.4/125)P by Fibercore were used as sensors. This optical fiber with 6.4 μm core diameter has additionally a 125 μm cladding and 155 μm polyimide coating diameter [14]. Because of the challenges in terms of handling the optical fibers, an additional protection, particularly in the ingress and egress from the CFRP, is needed [15]. Avoiding low radius bending caused by the boss geometry or other CFRP layers is of highest importance, since it could negatively influence the measurement quality, or even damage the optical fibers.

Figure 1: Stacking sequence of the used type 4 CPVs [13].

The configuration for protecting the optical fiber is shown in Figure 2. Directly behind the FC/APC plug, two protection tubes divided by a splice protection are used. The end of the 1.5 mm tube aligns with the end of the aluminum boss part or beginning of the CFRP. In the composite, only the PTFE capillary is used in the dome part, as also shown in Figure 3. It provides an additional protection in the areas in which the optical fiber leaves the fiber parallel orientation and is particularly exposed to the pressure from the winding tension of the newly wound layers.

Figure 2: Concept for protection of the optical fiber at ingress and leaving carbon fiber parallel orientation.

Figure 3: Optical fibers leaving the carbon fiber parallel orientation of a hoop layer.

2.2 Finite Element Models

Finite element models were developed to discuss the strains obtained with fiber optic sensors during SBT. Since the models were extensively discussed elsewhere [13, 16], only a brief introduction based on the mentioned publications is provided at this point.

The finite element analyses were performed using ANSYS Mechanical 2023 R1. ANSYS ACP Prep/Post was used as a dedicated tool for preparing the model of the composite pressure vessel. As a basis for the geometry definition, a 3D scan of the liner was derived using Shining 3D EinScan HX. The stacking sequence of the carbon fiber reinforced layers and their nominal thickness were derived from the used type 4 6.8-liter cylinder. For the material data of the carbon fiber, resin and liner material, data sheet values and experimental data from the literature were used [17-20]. The material data for the carbon reinforced unidirectional plies was then calculated with rules of mixture according to [21] under assumption of a process typical fiber volume ratio of 60 %. A summary of the material data used can be found in Table 1 and Table 2.

Engineering constant	Abbreviation	Value	Unit
Young's Modulus in fiber direction	E_1	133500	[MPa]
Young's Modulus perpendicular to fiber direction	E_2	6380	[MPa]
Shear Modulus	G_{21}	2100	[MPa]
Poisson's ratio	ν_{21}	0.35	–
Ply thickness	t	0.45	mm

Table 1: Material data of an unidirectional CFRP ply.

Engineering constant	Abbreviation	Value	Unit
Young's Modulus	E	3600	[MPa]
Shear Modulus	G	1340	[MPa]
Poisson's ratio	ν	0.34	–
Ply thickness	t	0.40	mm

Table 2: Material data of PET liner.

The model was meshed with second order solid elements (SOLID186) with one element per composite layer. To constrain the model, displacements in x, y and z directions were suppressed at boss and the opposite dome end of the cylinder. The internal pressure loading during an SBT is applied to the whole inner surface of the cylinder. The model with the corresponding coordinate system is shown in Figure 4.

Figure 4: Finite element model used for the comparison of strains with FOS.

3 EXPERIMENTAL STUDY

3.1 Integration of Fiber Optic Sensors

For a smooth integration into the wound structure, the optical fibers for each layer were prepared on cardboard tubes in advance and placed behind the carbon fiber spools on the winding machine shafts. The length of each FOS exceeded the length of fibers used for the winding of the monitored layer by 4 m plus the distance from the cardboard tube to the wound CPV on top. The additional length was needed for ingress and egress from the CPV as well as connection to the measurement devices.

The optical fiber was led over the carbon fiber rovings and the resin bath and brought together with the carbon fiber roving directly before the pay-out eye of the winding machine. This procedure allows to avoid the contact with the epoxy resin for all parts of the sensor, which must remain flexible to later prevent damage of the optic fiber. At the same time, the optical fiber is placed onto the rotating liner together with the carbon fiber ensuring a good agreement of their winding angles. Figure 5 shows the optical fiber placed on the shaft of the winding machine and led towards the wound pressure vessel.

Figure 5: Optical fiber (gold in the bottom right corner) placed on the winding machine.

For ingress and egress from the CFRP, the dome part with the aluminum boss was used. Before the winding process, the boss edges were rounded to ensure a sufficient radius of all edges and to eventually avoid low radius bending of the optical fiber. The optical fiber itself was positioned in a way that ensures high bending radius, even if the optical fiber leaves the orientation of the carbon fiber roving and is particularly exposed to bending e.g., by the next carbon fiber layers (see Figure 3).

The method of integration of the FOS and the protection concept led to an excellent survival rate of the optical fibers in the project. All of the 18 embedded sensors survived the integration and could be used for strain measurements in the finished component. No adjustment of the filament winding machine was needed.

3.2 Slow Burst Tests and Strain Measurements

All 15 cylinders were destructively tested in SBT. On the one hand, the tests allowed a check of the functionality of integrated FOS by measuring the occurring strains. On the other hand, SBT are a method to assess the performance of composite pressure vessels introduced by Mair [22-25]. Therefore, an assessment of the impact of integrated optical fiber on the performance of the CPV sample is possible.

In an SBT, the pressure in a CPV is increased by 20 % of test pressure per hour, which corresponds to 1.5 bar per minute in the case of the investigated CPVs. During the tests, distributed strain measurements were performed using an ultra-high resolution optical backscatter reflectometer OBR 4600 (Luna Inc.). One measurement was performed every 5 bar, which sums up to 180 measurements up to a minimum burst pressure of 900 bar [26]. For the comparison with finite element models, an

average strain value was calculated for each measurement throughout the area of interest. For the hoop layers, two full hoop windings in the middle of the cylindrical region were considered. In case of helical windings, three sections in the cylindrical region with a length of 20 cm were defined.

4 RESULTS

4.1 Strain Distribution in Slow Burst Tests

Figure 6 shows the strains in the fiber direction in a cylinder from one specimen of Sample A subjected to an SBT. The helical winding shows significantly lower strains than the hoop windings, which was expected considering the stress distribution in a cylinder loaded with internal pressure. A good agreement between the strains measured with FOS and those calculated with finite element models can be observed. For the hoop windings a divergence of less than 10 % is present. Deviation of the material data in fiber direction can be considered as a possible cause for this behavior. The strains in the helical windings show an excellent agreement between FOS and finite element models. In general, the fiber optic sensors deliver feasible strain values and a good bonding between CFRP layers and the optical fibers can be assumed.

Figure 6: Strain in fiber direction during slow burst test in a CPV from sample A.

4.2 Impact of Optical Fibers on the Performance in Slow Burst Tests

No clear impact of the embedded fiber optic sensors on the behavior of the composite structure could be observed based on the post-mortem pictures of destroyed CPVs. The failure mechanisms, which were characteristic for each sample, did not vary for the CPVs with integrated fibers.

The burst pressures of all investigated cylinders are shown in Figure 7. The CPVs equipped with FOS are marked with half-filled symbols. The sample names correspond to the explanation in Section 2.1.

Figure 7: Relative burst pressures of all tested cylinders.

In general, the burst pressure of the CPVs with FOS are comparable with the burst pressures of the CPVs without FOS. Also, no clear trend can be observed regarding the scattering of the burst pressures. However, for each of the tested samples, the lowest burst pressure is a value obtained on a CPV with embedded optical fibers. Dixon's Q test is performed to identify if the lowest burst pressure values can be considered as outliers, which would indicate a significant impact of the integrated FOS on the mechanical behavior of the CPV. Burst pressures are arranged in increasing order and the value of Q is calculated as follows [27]:

$$Q = \frac{gap}{range} = \frac{x_1 - x_2}{x_1 - x_n} \quad (1)$$

At 95 % confidence none of the burst pressure values can be considered an outlier.

5 CONCLUSIONS

In this study optical fibers were integrated into six type 4 composite pressure vessels under industrial conditions. Three optical fibers were embedded in each composite cylinder and used for monitoring of six composite layers. No adjustments to the winding machine were needed. A protection concept for the ingress and egress of the optical fiber was developed, which resulted in an excellent survival rate of the optical fibers.

Strain measurements were performed with the integrated fiber optic sensors in slow burst tests. The obtained strain data were compared with finite element simulations showing a good agreement.

All six composite pressure vessels with embedded optical fibers and nine composite pressure vessels of the same designs were destructively tested in slow burst tests. No differences in failure mechanisms were observed within the samples. Even though a slight decrease of the mean burst pressures was observed for the cylinders with embedded fiber optic sensors, no clear trend in the influence of the embedded optical fibers on the performance of composite cylinders can be stated. An increase of the samples' size would contribute to further clarification of the influence of embedded optical fibers on the performance of the composite pressure vessels.

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